

‘e-motive’: An investigation of Emotion and Meaning in Motion.

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Abstract

In collaboration with Philips a postgraduate research team at the Centre for Design Research investigated how context can influence the emotion and meaning of a set of product motions, such as opening or closing, turning and waving. The aim was to determine whether there was significant consistency in observer response to these motion scenarios, to inform the design process of key semantic considerations.

This project stemmed from the Philips project iCat that was designed to enable researchers to study behaviour, determine whether human interaction patterns can be mimicked and whether or not people recognise or even want such characteristics in robots. The aim was to facilitate a more intuitive interface between humans and appliances, providing richer interaction and a more sensorial experience.

The term e-motive was adopted as a working title to explain a new process of researching, which would highlight any inadequacies of the conventional design process to deal with the additional channel of movement. Derived from the two words emotion and movement, e-motive was descriptive of our preliminary objective of expressing emotions through movement.

Our main aim was to develop greater understanding around the process of designing movements into objects that could act as physical mediators of information and emotional content. In-order to consciously design movements, new methods and process were required if we were to develop additional ‘channels of expression’ into conventional industrial design practice. Intrinsic to the e-motive testing method, was the influence that ‘contextual’ factors had on the perceptions of both movement and emotions. To be able to fully specify and explicitly design a movement with an intended emotional message, it was found to be essential to separate the movement from any contextual interference. This was considered crucial to creating intentional emotional loading in objects, which could be derived irrespective of contextual influences. The fundamental problem was how to obtain a ‘contextually devoid’ response from a person to a movement.

It was found that while in some cases common perceptions of a motion differed from expectation, reliability of communicating emotion by motion was dependent upon observers having some shared formal semantics to comprehend context. As a consequence of this it was considered essential that intended context should be easily derived through the fundamental language of the form.

Introduction

This investigation, by the research team, based in the Centre for Design Research in Northumbria University, centred on gaining an understanding of people's perception of meaning conveyed by motions. The approach taken was to use 4D Sketching techniques, a form of motion prototyping, initially developed by Loe Feijs from TU/e in Eindhoven in, to investigate motion in concept and product, (Kyffin *et al*, 2003).

4D Sketching as a process involves mood-boarding motion clips, the basic modelling of form and key features, as either soft models, (e.g. card, foam, wood or clay mock-ups), or as virtual 3D models in computer animation environments, providing/assigning degrees of motion, (Young *et al*, 2005). 'Degrees of motion' refers to directional axes of freedom as well as types of movement, e.g. smooth, random, or sudden, etc. By this method a range of motions can be observed with a range of forms in a range of contexts, from which a grid of perceptions can be generated and analysed. This methodical, fundamental, approach is seen to provide keener insight into patterns of perceived meaning, (Buchenau and Fulton, 2000).

The generation of ideas for motion was achieved through motion referencing using web-based video clip libraries mainly, and motion sampling of hand movements. Typical forms and motion included, for example water: waves, bubbles, waterfalls, wakes, ice, ripples, steam and rain. Words were then generated to describe these forms and motions, and then these were categorised into modes.

Figure. 1 E-Motive Moodboards

Further ‘dimensional’ models/graphs were created for forms and motions, with axes such as Anthropometric/Abstract, and Static/Dynamic. In conjunction with ‘story-boarding’ the use of comic-strip style drawings of form and motion in context a range of perspectives were possible for analysing the meanings of motions.

In conclusion of the team’s initial investigation, guidance was drawn up for the future development of form and motion:

project foundation: 'words' taken from Team PHILIPS

6 Building in a directional aspect emphasises the view point of the mediator to the user.
A dot or sphere with direct resemblance to the eye.

4 In abstracting anthropomorphic features care has to be taken to avoid un-natural state.
Any form which has a resemblance to a head must be sympathetic to anthropomorphic anatomy. Otherwise associations with science fiction and aliens starts to complicate and confuse the main focus of the message.

3 Organic forms suggest breathing more effectively than mechanical motions.
Keeping it simple prevents the abstraction complicating the meaning to mechanical metaphors or interpretations.

2 Fast and sharp movements with rapid changes in velocity are best for attention seeking and have connotations with danger.
Dynamic movement catches the eye and formal qualities are taken from the thorns of plants and the standing on end of hair.

5 Patterns of movement are less appropriate than one body of motion in communicating surprise and danger.
This is found to be because of systematic associations that are predictable and therefore not shocking.

4 Rounded forms imply 'play' rather than 'danger'.
Due to our genetic disposition we have a preference for softer curved forms, that is illustrated in the young of all species.

3 Changing the form can have a huge impact on the perception of the same movement.
When the form resembled venetian blinds the parallel between 'product' became the most dominant factor in influencing the response.
Connotations of venetian blinds in every day life distracts from the movement, thus the slats were changed to triangular shapes.

For one 'super beacon' to work effectively in communicating more than one emotion. Rather than using disparate motions to achieve changes in emotional state, it should be facilitated through a family of similar motions that can express multiple emotions.

e-motive project 09.08.2004
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Figure. 2 Project Foundation

1. Building in a directional aspect will emphasise the viewpoint of the mediator to the user. For example, a dot or a sphere resembling an eye.
2. In abstracting anthropomorphic features, care has to be taken to avoid un-natural states. For example, any form that bears resemblance to a head must be sympathetic to anthropomorphic anatomy otherwise associations may complicate and confuse the main focus of the message.
3. Organic forms suggest 'breathing' more effectively than mechanical motions. Keeping it simple prevents abstraction complicating the meaning of mechanical metaphors or interpretations.
4. Fast and sharp movements with rapid changes in velocity are best for attention seeking and have connotations with danger. Dynamic movement catches the eye.
5. Patterns of movement are less appropriate than one body of motion in the communication of surprise or danger, because systematic associations that are predictable are not shocking.
6. Rounded forms imply 'Play' rather than 'Danger'. There is a natural preference for softer curved forms, which are seen in the young of many species.

7. Changing the form can have a huge impact on the perception of the same movement.

The experience of the initial e-motive project work was applied to the design of this investigation. (Weerdesteijn *et al*, 2005)

Test development

To create an open and free environment conducive to the creative process the team began by 'brainstorming' around three main focus areas: the smoke detector, UV intensity beach indicator and the baby monitor. This led to scenario writing that concentrated on both the role of the user and the product throughout the day. This process facilitated a better understanding of the use and interaction that occurred between the user and product.

4D sketches, models of motion, were then developed for the e-motive pilot testing. This involved quite an investment of time as the modelling of form and motion required a lot of reflection to understand and improve the 4D sketches as effective communicators of meaning. For example, the smoke detector adopted a 'looking' element for smoke but on reflection this motion seemed to be counter intuitive. It was suggested on review by Philips that the team should try and develop a motion along the lines of 'sniffing' hopefully producing a more appropriate means of communication for locating smoke than 'looking'.

For the UV intensity beach indicator, the main issues were concerned with how to best communicate protection to a large number of people. In the context of the beach, flags were chosen as the design metaphor which developed into the use of flower forms. The problem became one of 'how to distinguish when a flower communicates protection'.

For instance:

Does a flower closing up and protecting itself or a flower opening out and casting a shadow similar to a parasol communicate protection more in the context of a UV intensity beach indicator?

Do we, as individuals, place ourselves in the position of the mediator or view it as a separate entity?

An attempt was made to establish whether literal connotations with flowers could be reduced to a minimum and still provoke the same response of protection using abstract form. It was found that without a recognisable form the participants would have to make an informed decision as to what the form resembled. It was also determined that the most positive responses for protection came from watching something moving into shade.

As the testing developed, for example with the baby monitor, there was a need to streamline questioning, narrowing the focus to the two most appropriate questions:

‘What were your feelings towards the movement?’

‘Within the ‘context’ of ‘a baby in a cot’ does your feeling towards the movement change in anyway?’

It was also found that offering three images for the same context would often produce conflicting messages for the participants. Therefore it was decided to simply use one image to set context. Another observation was in relation to the participant’s involvement in the testing process. Coming in ‘cold’ to the project, the participants became more confident and at ease with the situation only after they had completed the first clip. This was thought to effect the quality of the first response, and led to the application of a ‘dummy clip’ that was provided at the beginning of the test to allow the participant time to warm up and become more involved in the project.

Utilising contextual cues was an important issue. For the smoke detector to stimulate a response for ‘sniffing’, we repeated the same test but upside down, in an attempt to place it spatially in a more conventional position that an individual would expect to see a smoke detector. More 4D sketches were produced. These had the addition of holes taking the form of nostrils in the hope of prompting the sense of ‘sniffing’.

As the pilot testing progressed it was found that use of recognisable form enabled people to more easily make associations with the movement. It was at this stage that the team utilised computer animated designs using Cinema 4D software to produce smooth moving models that could be completed in half the time it took to make the soft model

4D sketches. The accuracy that could be achieved through computer animations was essential when the movements were looked at more closely. It was also found that the irregularities inadvertently produced using hands could be read as part of the desired movement. This could obviously be a source of conflict in the participant's mind, as to what was supposed to be intentional movement and what was merely a limitation of the communication medium.

Key to this investigation was whether or not an individual could make a range of emotional responses to one family of movements. For example, in the case of the baby monitor the team needed to have a range of communicative states, including: sleeping, stirring, babbling, crying and screaming, to be choreographed through the product form mediator.

These observations of prototype testing informed the development of the e-motive test method.

Method

The e-motive test involved three concept scenarios, used as vehicles to explore meaning in motion. These were: A smoke alarm, a UV intensity beach indicator and a baby monitor. 4D Sketching techniques were used to investigate these contexts through scenarios.

The intention was to gather the participant's initial response to the movement clips, followed by the question 'why?' and then rating the intensity of the emotion on a scale from 1 to 10. The second questions used Ekman's 'basic emotions' surprise, joy, sadness, disgust, fear and anger that were also very similar to the work of Pieter Desmet, (Desmet, 2002). To offer a more balanced choice of negative and positive emotions we added the word 'calm' to account for this discrepancy in-order to create a fair test. This had the effect of directing participant response if they experienced difficulty associating emotion to movement. The final question was intended to place the movement into a context by using three images and it was asked whether this changed their opinion on the movements (Chao *et al*, 2004).

test protocol - method of approach

First we aim to ask the participants to give us their immediate initial thoughts on the movement shown. This offers a totally unbiased approach to the movement shown.

Followed by asking them why, to enable us to understand the reason behind their response. We envisage this to be an important question as there is likely to be an enormous amount of 'personal experience' built into their initial answers.

To achieve a more directed set of answers, we are using what are known as the 'basic emotions' Ekman (1971) surprise, joy, sadness, disgust, fear and anger. For the purposes of our testing we are also using the word 'calm'. By offering the participants a choice of words we are more likely to get a useful set of data.

Last of all, we will add in the context to see what effect the environment has on the understanding of the movement. Whether or not it has the effect of strengthening or weakening the response to the motion when put in context.

For all of the questions we will also ask the participants to rate the intensity of their response from 'a little - a lot'. This is important to get away from crude binary data in order to build up a more comprehensive set of data. For us to encompass the various degrees of freedom of motion.

From this data we hope to produce a set of graphs and visual maps to help us draw from it any correlations or further questions for exploration.

The figure displays a test protocol form with two columns of questions. Each question includes a rating scale from 1 to 7. The questions are:

- 1. What is your initial response to the movement?
- 1a. Can you explain why?
- 1b. On this scale rate the intensity of this emotion.
- 2. Which word would you relate to the motion?
- 2a. On this scale how relevant do you think this word is to the motion?
- 3. When this context has your understanding of the movement changed?

Below the form is a fan of cards labeled "basic emotions + calm" with numbers 1 through 7. To the right of the cards are three images labeled "context images": a person in a car, a person in a boat, and a person in a field.

At the bottom left, it says "e-motive project 17.08.2004" with names "dan pezzutti", "richard sharp", and "stuart pill". At the bottom right, there are logos for "northumbria UNIVERSITY" and "PHILIPS", and the number "075".

Figure. 3 Test Protocol

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Through participant testing, the data gathered suggested which movements induced the required emotional response. The final stage of the investigation was to create a homogenous blend between both form and movement where these two channels of communication compliment each other. Participants were also asked to view four separate movements each at three different speeds after watching five videos of babies in the five states, sleeping, stirring, babbling, crying and screaming.

The test paper was completely numerically based with each clip requiring the participant to rate the suitability of the movement to one of the five states on a scale from 1 to 10, with 10 representing the most liked and 1 the least liked. This allowed the collation of a large amount of data, to be processed through excel, producing a range of visual diagrams that would communicate the findings.

These tests also used the four established movements in three minute animation clips that followed a specified narration of the baby sleeping, stirring, sleeping, babbling, stirring, screaming and back to sleeping. Participants were simply required to fill in the boxes on a test sheet relating the baby's state to the movements they saw.

key to baby monitor degrees of freedom

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Figure. 4 Degrees of Freedom

To create a 'control' for the testing of Freedoms Of Movement, which would be directly comparable with the previous work of the team. Computer animations were not used for the smoke detector but instead the tried and tested 4D sketch techniques of soft models were utilised. In this way observations could be made regarding these two different techniques, allowing the computer animations to be judged on merit as to whether or not they offer value as part of the 4D sketching palette of tools.

Results

One of the main theories to develop from the research regarded the hierarchy of thought that individuals follow in order to comprehend movement in 4D sketches. It was observed, and notes through verbal reporting, that there was an order to the participants acknowledgement and comprehension of 'form', 'motion' and 'emotion'. We noticed that if a participant made no mental link with the form they found it hard to describe and communicate any meaning to us, (Lakoff, 1999). Where participants exhibited a poor level of comprehension of the form, they then experienced difficulty in engaging further with the test. This highlighted the importance that the formal qualities and semantics

play in the role of setting a contextual awareness that the participants could recognise. It also highlighted the difference in ability of participants to make associations in the first place with a form. Consequently if a person did not understand the form they were not then able to make any associations with the movement to then acknowledge emotional cues. This demonstrated that it is essential to create a form that is suggestive of the context. It seems that the most effective way in which to communicate movement is to create forms that are fundamentally easily identifiable, fitting into prior knowledge and mental models of what already exists and has been commonly experienced, (Isle, 2000).

Figure. 5 Motion Follows Form

	Negative	positive
	Incomprehensible	recognisable
Object	No associations or parallels can be drawn from everyday life.	Links with nature, and through the learning and conditioning that we experience through society and cultures.
Motion	The movement can only be described in very literal terms.	Applying this is 'a prior' knowledge to the form Enables an understanding to be formed regarding the movement.
Emotion	Without any connections or prompts with everyday life feelings of indifference emerge. As the forms and motions have no relation to anything we understand.	This leads to a feeling or opinion towards either the form or movement to be made.

In this way a form may achieve a level of 'invisibility', which cannot be achieved purely by simplifying and abstracting form. 'Invisibility' of the form refers to the deflection of the observer's attention from the form as greater attention is drawn towards the motive behaviour. Our objectives were to purely elicit the participant's response to movement, which posed the problem of controlling any external influences that may have an affect. However, to test any movement requires the creation of a 'mediator' that the movement can be manifest within. This physical representation of movement is illustrated through a 'vehicle' that has its own language and connotations that can obscure the fundamental emotional values of the movement if not well considered. This is an interesting point that questioned our initial thoughts, that the form should just be kept as simple as possible, bland in colour, without texture and devoid of any styling.

From the 'Degrees Of Freedom' testing it was found that at slow speeds the form is the most important factor in communicating meaning, whilst at fast speeds the form becomes blurred and distorted thus making the movement itself the determining factor. The tests also highlighted how soft forms moving at fast speeds are intrinsically linked with sharp forms moving at slow speeds.

In the case of the Baby Monitor, the 'stirring' and 'babbling' represented transitional states and therefore required more complex movements and degrees of freedom to express those more subtle emotions. These transitional parts of a sequence of movement represent moments of anticipation and significance where a decision must be made. This is similar to the changes in state of a rattle snake where undisturbed it will move organically, but if alarmed will utilise a random motion for rattling its tail, suggesting choice. If the threat dissipates then the snake will return to organic movements however if action must be taken a mechanistic movement in the form of a strike will be made. This is linked to another theory we proposed, for 'organic', 'random' and 'mechanical' categories, which are important to transitions in all movements. This was a principle that was observed by the team throughout the project.

Discussion

A number of concepts were considered, prototyped, tested and reflected upon in this investigation, providing a wealth of experience for the design team that has taken some time to distil in terms of intent to apply to product design. In summary the conclusions were as follows.

If a form cannot be comprehended by an individual, then they are far more likely to use their own prior knowledge and personal experiences to derive meaning from the movement. For instance, with irrelevance to the formal qualities of whether it's soft or hard. When the movement is fast the form cannot be comprehended and has less significance to the overall emotional associations made. We would suggest that once a soft form had been recognised and then moved at speed the emotional response would be one more associated with surprise than fear. However if the formal qualities were sharp and moved with speed we would expect to elicit the emotional response of fear from a participant. In conclusion a motion that is fast enough to obscure the formal qualities may always cause fear in participants. However, if the formal qualities were made explicit before the movement then we would argue a different emotional response would be provoked depending on the formal language. For the best emotional effect it is essential to create a form that is suggestive of the intended movement, easily identifiable, fitting into prior knowledge and mental models of what already exists.

Slow movements communicate emotional meaning through form more effectively than fast motions where form becomes blurred and distorted thus making the movement itself the determining factor. It was also found that transitional states, representing moments of anticipation and significance where a decision must be made, required more complex movements and greater degrees of freedom.

In order to prove the implications that 'context' has on emotional meaning, further investigations would be required. Such an investigation might involve taking a product motion with a specific emotional meaning, and placing it into a conflicting context to see how sincerely possessed by the form in motion the communicated emotion is. This would illustrate the 'falseness' that hides behind the terminology 'emotional objects'. It is concluded that an inanimate object does not possess emotions, it merely elicits an emotional response from its users. This subtle difference is important to recognise, if we are not to continue building in fallacies that the user will never accept as genuine.

Conclusion

In summary an important shift was made regarding our thinking behind emotions and the 'organic', 'random' and 'mechanical' portrayal of objects. In the beginning they had suggested that emotions might be designed into objects, however it came to be realised that emotions were the users interpretations and responses to product motions. This resulted in our final decision to change the title from e-motive to i-motive in reflection of the 'interaction' required to elicit the emotion in the user.

To create an inanimate object that appears to have emotions requires a sophisticated approach to its capability for adaptation. Enabling a greater amount of adaptability within the objects would facilitate an intrinsic synergy between both the object and its contextual surroundings, making it more appropriate to the environment. As the object becomes 'driven' by external influences in real time from its current contextual environment, an accurate and believable portrayal of emotional content can be more readily achieved.

Further investigation and analysis is essential to obtain more information regarding two way communication between object and human, but it is clear that we are significantly

affected by the environment which implies that our objects must also be affected by the context in-order to remain relevant to our situation.

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